

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT OF "INDEPENDENT WORK OF A STUDENT IN A GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOL" BASED ON THE CONCEPT OF "SUBSYSTEM OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY"

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Abstract

The article emphasizes that the need to form an educational space in line with the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution makes it urgent to rework the theoretical and technological directions related to its implementation. Although the discovery of the nature of the training system, which is understood as a way of implementing the aforementioned education, and the discovery of new approaches require theoretical and technological research, the theoretical and technological aspects of organizing independent work in the training process in accordance with the modern educational environment have not been sufficiently studied, and this is why, as proven in practice, the majority of people with general education have difficulty performing independent cognitive functions. Therefore, the theoretical and technological directions of applying independent work in the training process carried out in modern conditions should be determined, and the "gap" in this direction should be eliminated.

The research work shows that it is logical to approach the implementation of modern education as a complete (organized system). In this system, students are involved in independent and non-independent cognitive activity. These types of activities exist depending on the emergent nature of the learning system. The mentioned types of activities exist as aspects of the unit. They are subsystems of the learning process of the "large system" (this term belongs to C.A. Shaporinsky, see: [17]). Here, in determining theoretical and technological directions based on the "system-structural approach", in selecting independent works, and in transforming them into a system and using them, reference should be made to the dialectics inherent in the said approach.

Keywords: freedom, independence, activity, relatively finished element of activity, subsystem of activity, independent work, learner-centered learning, psycho-didactic requirements, thinking, types of mental activity.

Relevance of the topic. The need to shape an educational space in line with the challenges of the 4th industrial revolution makes it necessary to rework the theoretical and technological directions related to its implementation. It naturally comes to mind that revealing the nature of the aforementioned "learning understood as a way of implementing education" (Prof. N.M. Kazimov) system and discovering new approaches requires theoretical and technological research. In connection with this necessity, a training system should be formed so that the student, who enters that system as a party (main component), acquires the qualities of a creative personality in accordance with the requirements (challenges) of the 21st century. In other words, the learner, as a person belonging to the "techno-democratic-information society", can become a subject of creative experience, independent thinking and attitude to what is perceived in the learning process. Therefore, in the learning process, the learner should be educated as a subject of independent cognitive activity by entering the learning situation.

Despite what we have said, the theoretical and technological aspects of organizing independent work,

which is an integral part of the learner-centered learning process in a modern (adequate to the challenges of the 21st century) educational environment, have not been sufficiently studied, which is why, as proven in practice, the majority of people with general education have difficulty performing independent cognitive functions related to many of the questions they encounter. Therefore, in the training process carried out in modern conditions, the theoretical and technological directions of organizing (implementing and managing) the independent work of students should be determined, and the "gap" in this direction should be eliminated.

Based on what we have said, we claim that the interpretation of the concept of "independent work of a student in a general education school" based on the concept of "subsystem of educational activity" is a topical cognitive issue.

Methodological basis of the study. In the process of conducting the research, the "System-structural approach", which originated from L. Bertalanfi's idea of "System Analysis" [8;8] and was formed as an important branch of dialectics and rose to the level of its alternative, scientific-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal relationships of

its forms, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used as a methodological basis.

The goal is to clarify options for more effectively incorporating and managing students' independent work into the learning process in secondary schools.

Interpretation of generalizations based on materials obtained in research work. Four directions are most evident in the activity of the individual: the activity of understanding oneself and the world surrounding one with its values; the activity of preserving what one has achieved with uniqueness; the activity of changing the world and oneself (corresponding to the degree of elevation from biological to social existence); the activity of entering into a relationship normalized by human values.

Professor L.B. Itelson notes that a relatively finished element of activity in one direction or another, aimed at solving a simple current problem, is called work. In our opinion, from the point of view of approaching the activity of the individual as a system, it would be more appropriate to use the expression "subsystem" instead of the term "relatively finished element". [13, 169]

Work, which is a subsystem of the personality's activity system, can be performed by the subject in independent or non-independent ways. There is a dialectical connection between activity and work, which is its subsystem. What we have said is also fully applicable to the learning activity and its subsystems. In the learning process, a student can freely perform a current task both with the intervention of the teacher (preferably with his facilitation) and without direct assistance, performing mental and practical activities. The second case retains its essence in the concept of "independent work of the student".

Understanding and revealing the essence of the concept of "independent work" is closely related to the concept of "independence of thinking", which forms the psychological basis of students' cognitive activity and performance. Understanding the essence of independence of thinking not only allows us to understand the essence of independent work, but also allows us to determine the degree of independence of students in different age groups, without which it is impossible to organize students' independent work in practice.

In order to organize students' independent work in the learning process, it is necessary to correctly understand the scientific and psychological essence of independence of thinking. [7; 31]

Independence of thinking, in addition to constituting the psychological basis of students' independent work, is in practice a very broad property of the mind and reflects a number of other properties of the mind, including criticality. Without the participation of the criticality of the mind, there can be no independent activity of thinking, independent cognitive process, and independent work of students. The critical nature of the mind is necessary in independent activity so that the individual can evaluate himself, consider and compare the results of his activities, point out mistakes and shortcomings, and verify the correctness of the path chosen to solve the problem. Otherwise, it is difficult to call independence a complete, complete characteristic

of thinking. [7; 27- 39] It is worth emphasizing here that one of the main factors determining the effectiveness of a learner's activity is his or her possession of a meta-cognitive "cognitive action experience" - a metacognitive method.

It should also be noted that there are those who rightly disagree with the idea of limiting the independence of thought to criticism alone. For example, S.L. Rubinstein believes that not only the criticality of the mind, but also a number of other psychological abilities are included in the sphere of activity of independence of thinking. Among them, first of all, it is necessary to mention willpower. [15; 525] M.M. Mehdizadeh agrees with this idea and notes that students' independent work, no matter what option it takes, faces certain difficulties. These must be eliminated. It is known that a student with weak willpower cannot cope with the task set before him. [9;184] Thus, volitional activity also becomes, in a certain sense, a component of independence of thought.

According to M.A. Ismikhonov, independence of thinking is primarily expressed in the student's ability to solve a certain cognitive problem by his own strength, showing mental activity, taking a critical approach to his own activities, and being independent in thought. The student's independence in training is closely related to his activity. [12; 19]

Undoubtedly, the student's activity is an important condition for his independence: independence is possible on the basis of a certain mental and practical activity of the student. Activity, in turn, requires a certain independence from the student, the more independence the student shows in learning, the more active he becomes. One can agree with the views of M.M. Mehdizadeh and M.A. Ismikhonov.

The methodological basis of the problem is the connection of the category of "freedom" in philosophy with education. In philosophy, the concept of "freedom" is rightly considered, on the one hand, as the relationship between freedom and necessity in the life of large masses of people, in its general-historical plan, and on the other hand, in the subjective-moral aspect, it is understood as the internal activity of the individual. As M.G. Myslivchenko noted, in the first aspect the formula "freedom" is most closely related to politics, while in the second aspect it is related to pedagogy and psychology. [5; 192]

M.M. Mehdizadeh, however, linked freedom with activity and wrote that the independence of the individual is formed in the process of active participation in public life, including education, that is, in the process of active social activity. The development of a person's independence, that is, his ability to make independent decisions, practically demonstrates the decision he makes, the ability to solve any task in accordance with the interests of the social group he belongs to, and at the same time his responsibility towards that group. "It is precisely through the independent solution of the tasks set by life that the responsibility of the individual develops, becoming an organic function of his independence" - A.I. Romanyuk is right in his opinion, and in this regard M.M. Mehdizadeh shows that only one remark can be added to all this: "A person's sense of responsibility, in the context of his internal activity, his

creative and managerial-executive activities, is essentially considered the main line of his independence". [5; 193-194]

Although we have no serious objections to what has been said, we see a need to add that the concepts of "freedom", "independence" and "activity" should be viewed in a dialectical relationship for all aspects. Thus, a person accepts his freedom according to the degree to which he understands reality and is able to change it. Understanding reality and changing it, and gaining relevant experience depend on the independence of the personality and its corresponding activity. At the same time, what is perceived, the experience of understanding, the experience of changing reality further increases the independence of the personality. Therefore, the concepts of "freedom", "independence", and "activity" can belong to a system of categories that condition each other and reflect the level of social formation of personality. The great importance of independent work in shaping the independence of the individual, developing the activity of students, strengthening their will, and overcoming difficulties encountered when completing tasks is undeniable. In the learning process, the issues of "developing students' independence" and "organizing and managing independent work" are interdependent, performing cause and effect functions consistently and mutually.

Based on our theoretical analyses and work experience, we consider it appropriate to understand independent work as follows: *In the learning process, the subsystem of the student's activity aimed at completing the task that involves him in the learning situation, which takes place without direct assistance, is called his independent work.*

For clarity, we consider it appropriate to comment on some aspects highlighted in the definition of a student's independent work in the learning process.

As can be seen, the definition considers the student's independent work as a subsystem of his learning activity. This emphasizes that the dialectical relationship that must exist between the system and the subsystem also exists between the learning activity (system) and the student's independent work (part). That is, the student's independent work is based on the implementation of all didactic tasks set before the learning process. Therefore, the set goal must be understood by the student, that goal must become the object of satisfaction of the student's cognitive needs, and in order to fulfill the requirements of the set task, he must become the subject of the activity he is involved in. In other words, the task must create a learning situation, which is an integral part (element) of the structure of learning activity.

By the way, let us emphasize that educational activity is multifaceted. Although training is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all its aspects. Educational activity is a type of human activity, a specific form of social activity of the individual. In the structure of the mentioned activity, along with the teaching situation (or tasks), teaching operations, control and assessment are included as components. Teaching activity begins with the solution of teaching tasks. Although its essence is reflected in the

meaning of the task, its character is related to the meaning of "teaching." Teaching tasks involve the discovery and mastery of general methods (principles, regularities) for solving various problems and specific practical issues by students in their own teaching activities. [2; 150]

In the process of independent work, the relationship between the manager, the managed, and the training material is changing and developing. The unity, systematicity, completeness, comprehensiveness, dependence, non-contradiction, and regularity of independent work should be expected.

Organizing and managing independent work is a purposeful mental activity of the teacher, an element in solving the cognitive problem of a didactic nature facing him. Most importantly, it has algorithmic and heuristic aspects.

Independent work as a subsystem has relative independence. Its means of organization and regulation are questions, tasks, and issues. [10; 313-322]

In the learning process, independent work is aimed at performing relatively independent functions, but these functions arise from the general goals of the process. The place of independent work in the learning process is determined by the coordination and management logic of the components of this process.

It is worth emphasizing that the training process is an organized system, complete with various approaches to it. [1; 268-274] Some of them have remained in the history of pedagogical thought, some have become subsystems of a more perfect system, have become included in it. Independent work is applied, manifested, and fulfills the "enabling function" in accordance with the emergent nature of the system to which it belongs. It has a special place in all stages of active learning (learner-centered learning - italics ours), which currently has a special place in general education schools. [11; 447-450], [14; 268-272]

The task for organizing independent work is mainly determined by the teacher for didactic purposes in accordance with the degree of independence of the student or students. The teacher performs the organizational-regulatory functions with a task that has a certain logical form. The main feature here is the lack of interference in the process of completing the task of the learner, ensuring the conditions for his independent activity. Independent work, being a subsystem of the learning process, has the property of time limitation. It can be applied at different stages of the learning process. Independent work accelerates the development of the learner, expands the possibilities for performing specific educational-cognitive and educational-organizational functions, and ensures good management of the learning process.

There are a number of requirements for students' independent work, and it is also possible to divide these requirements into types and classify them. The following psycho-didactic requirements for independent work can be attributed to them: 1. Independent work is designed based on the didactic tasks that are set in advance.

The didactic task of each independent work is to contain two important directions:

- 1) The overall goal of the training process:

a) the assimilation of the experience gained by mankind in the process of its historical development: b) the experience of its preservation: c) to direct oneself towards the preparation of acquiring the creative experience necessary for the civilization and freedom of man and the society to which he belongs: d) to direct oneself towards the acquisition of qualities that condition the coexistence of people who are organically connected with the previous three goals, and the opening of the window of the world for them,

2) Making the training process a well-managed process.

2. To organize and manage independent work, it is necessary to determine its location and the form of covering students.

Independent work can be attributed to all stages of the learning process, depending on its location:

a) justification of learning and actualization of past experience;

b) acquisition of knowledge;

c) application and systematization of knowledge;

d) evaluation of the process and results by the teacher and students themselves.

According to the form of covering students, it is determined as a) individual, b) pair, c) group, d) frontal.

3. The duration of independent work, the coverage of acquired knowledge, the degree of difficulty of new knowledge, and its suitability to the potential capabilities of students should be determined. Therefore, it should be clarified which of the various types included in the nomenclature of independent work will be applied.

4. The type of assignment should be chosen in advance and the teacher should think carefully about the formulation of the assignment. It is also important to seriously consider the capabilities of the school, the teacher's own training, the content of the training material, and the capabilities of the student (or students).

5. The conditions and requirements of the task should be clear to the learner. It is possible that the task for joint work with the learner is formed as a logical continuation of the work carried out, and in this case there is no need for additional explanations and instructions. If there is, then the learner must be given necessary and clarifying instructions.

6. Consistency, systematicity, and development should be expected in the application of independent work. The importance of this work should be kept in focus in order to prepare the student for independent and free education and life.

7. In the independent work of students, it is important to generalize, systematize, apply knowledge in changed situations, and include new elements.

The implementation of independent work should be based on the acquired knowledge, habits and skills, life experience, and observations, while maintaining the requirement to direct the student to the acquisition of more general knowledge, skills, habits, and experience. Independent work should lead to the improvement of the student's interest and inclinations in learning with its content, fun, and logic. Independent work should encourage the development of the ability to

make (correct and fair) assessments, which is considered one of the most important personal qualities of the learner.

8. The independent work system should maintain the unity of mental and practical activity. During independent work, the algorithmic and heuristic aspects of the student's mental activity should develop in unity, and in order for him to form a subject of management in his own activity, the working conditions should be improved by the correct guidance of the educator. The educator's guidance should be constantly adjusted in accordance with specific conditions.

It is shown that some of the classifications put forward as types of independent work in pedagogical literature should be attributed to the functional aspect of independent work (work aimed at mastering knowledge, forming and testing skills and habits), some to the level of independence of students during independent work (example-based, reconstruction and creative work), some to the source of independent work (book-based, reference literature, problem-solving and exercises, etc.), some to the degree of assistance from the educator (non-independent, semi-independent, fully independent work), and some to the form of organization of independent work (frontal, group, pair and individual work). It is emphasized that types of independent work can have different content depending on the characteristics of individual subjects and the specific teaching situation. [10;300-313]

The theoretical and practical path of dialectical unity of independent and dependent work of students as subsystems of a single process has not been worked out in all detail. In this work, the following points should be paid attention to:

1) The course of the educational process in accordance with the set didactic goals and the results of the students' activities depend largely on the level of development of two important aspects of their mental activity - analytical (algorithmic) and heuristic types, and their functioning in unity.

2) The direction and speed of a learner's development depend on the types of activities he is involved in and their regulation. At the same time, the developmental characteristics of the learner's personality are manifested in the activities he is involved in.

Based on these two logical arguments, it can be said that the learning process should be based on the level of development of both types of mental activity of the learner (algorithmic and heuristic), and should be aimed at their further development (ensuring their unity). Independent work should contain these aspects as a subsystem of learning activity.

The independent work system and its nomenclature, which corresponds to the logic of the learning process, includes the optimal relationships of the algorithmic and heuristic activities of the learners, which we consider practical and which we have used in our work experience to achieve effective results, are as follows:

1. A type of programmed or unprogrammed independent work aimed at transforming the goal set for the training process into an object of satisfying the needs of the learner (or learners).

We include the following types of independent work in this type:

1) Independent work related to understanding the usefulness of the material for teaching, development, and further activity;

2) Independent work that guides students to learn the material with fun and attractive shades;

3) Independent work that serves to create a problem situation;

2. The type of independent work (programmed or unprogrammed) that is applied when knowledge and methods of action are mainly transferred in a ready-made form.

According to this type, we include the following types of independent work related to intellectual activity: 1) independent work that requires updating and recalling what has been learned in the past, 2) training, independent work that requires applying an important rule or law to similar situations, 3) interpretative and explanatory independent work: 4) independent work that requires reasoning, 5) independent work related to algorithmization, 6) independent work related to the application of knowledge in changed situations: 7) independent work related to discussion, etc.

Types of independent work related mainly to practical activities: 1) independent work of an educational-practical nature: 2) independent work of a social-practical nature.

3. Cognitive-search (heuristic) type of independent work applied during problem-based learning.

We include the following types of independent work to this type:

1) Independent work applied to problematic interpretation: elimination of contradictions, independent study of the material not revealed (in the teacher's interpretation) by the student, and generalization.

2) Independent work applied to partial search.

3) Independent work guided by the application of problematic issues, questions, exercises: provocative independent work; constructive, defining independent work; experimental-search independent work; logical-search independent work, etc.

4. Creative independent work type.

We distinguish the following types of this type of independent work: 1) artistic-figurative; 2) scientific-creative; 3) constructive-technical; 4) experimental-creative.

Result. It is logical to approach the implementation of modern education as a complete (organized system). In this system, learners are involved in independent and non-independent cognitive activity. These types of activity exist in dependence on the emergent nature of the learning system. These types of activity exist as aspects of the unit. They are subsystems of a

larger system - the learning process. Here, based on a system-structural approach, the dialectics inherent in this approach should be referred to in determining theoretical and technological directions, selecting independent works, and transforming them into a system and using them.

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